

A Game-based Upper Limb AROM Measurement System for Older Adults

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Abstract: At present, the aging problem is becoming more and more serious, which undoubtedly causes people's attention to the life quality of the elderly. Active range of motion (AROM) is an important index to judge the ability of daily functional activities of the elderly. Therefore, it is very important to obtain the AROM data of the elderly quickly and accurately. The traditional method of measuring the range of motion (ROM) is to measure the passive range of motion (PROM) with a goniometer by nurses, which cannot accurately reflect the elderly's active ability in the daily life. In order to overcome the shortcomings of traditional methods, the AROM measurement system has been developed. However, in the current AROM measurement system, the elderly is guided to participate in ROM measurement. In this paper, we propose a game-based upper limb AROM measurement system. In the system, the joint coordinates of the player are measured by the depth image sensor, and the AROM is calculated automatically and objectively by using the coordinates. From the experimental results, the average flexion value measured by our system is 21.6 degrees larger than that measured by the goniometer. The average abduction value measured by our system is 24.1 degrees larger than that measured by goniometer. This result means that the elderly can stretch better through a game in our measurement system. In order to encourage the elderly to participate more in the game, a questionnaire survey was conducted on the elderly's views of the game. From the analysis results, we find that the merit factor and design factor of the game have a great impact on the players' experience in the game. The research results provide us with ideas for the improvement of the measurement system in the future.

Keywords: AROM, Game, older Adults, Interest

I. INTRODUCTION

The world's population is aging rapidly. According to the latest data from WHO, from 2020 to 2050, the proportion of people over 60 years old will double from 11% to 22%. In the same period, the absolute number of people aged 60 years old and over is expected to increase from 605 million to 2 billion [1,2]. The 2002 Madrid International Plan of Action on Aging (MIPAA) issued in the Second World Assembly on Aging, highlighted the essential to consider older persons in development planning. It also stressed that older persons should be able to participate equitably in and benefit from development outcomes to promote their health and well-being. Society should provide them with a favorable environment. Due to the deterioration of aging, more and more scholars begin to pay attention to the quality of life of the elderly, which

is called the successful aging [4-10]. Generally speaking, successful aging refers to that the elderly can have good physical movement function, good cognitive function, positive mental health, good social function and healthy and happy life. In order to achieve this goal, ROM is an important parameter to judge the ability of daily functional activities of the elderly [11].

The ability of the upper limb to participate in sports and activities of daily life depends on its range of motion [12, 13, 14]. ROM has a significant effect on flexibility, balance and muscle strength of the elderly [15, 16, 17]. ROM measurement can be divided into active range of motion (AROM) and passive range of motion (PROM). AROM was measured without any help and PROM was measured with the assistance of someone to move the subject's upper limb. So the main difference between AROM and PROM is the initiative of joint motion. At present, PROM is mainly measured

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Fig. 1: Scene transition of automatic AROM measurement system.

by goniometer in clinical practice. In this method, clinicians need to move the arm of the elderly and determine the range of motion through their subjective judgment [18, 19, 20]. Therefore, there are subjective differences in the results. Compared with PROM, AROM measurement is more accurate due to the lack of subjective evaluation. In addition, AROM can reflect the ability of daily activities and motor function of the elderly better [21,22,23]. However, the current AROM measurement system requires the elderly to pose according to the instructions. It guides participants into a few boring specific poses. The effect of self-interest of the elderly on the results is not considered in the measurement. Under the positive influence of interest, the elderly will try to raise their hands higher as they can.

Fig.2: Equipment layout of AROM measurement system.

Fig. 3: The example of game playing picture.

In the real-time monitoring, considering the importance of objectivity in ROM measurement and the stimulation of measurement interest, an automatic

AROM measurement system based on wipe game is proposed. In this system, we strive to achieve two goals. The first goal is to realize the automatic measurement of AROM for the elderly. The other is to get a practical value of AROM which can reflect the real life ability. In order to achieve the latter goal, we give up the boring guiding posture in the traditional AROM measurement system, and replace it with a game to enable the elderly to cooperate actively.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Image-Based PROM Measurement

The traditional method of PROM measurement is using common goniometer, square goniometer and electronic goniometer. However, this measurement method needs strict operational, professional abilities and it's very troublesome. Due to the dependence of the method on the surveyor, the subjective measurement error is inevitable. In order to overcome these shortcomings, some researchers use digital cameras to take pictures of joint motion posture, and directly measure the ROM of joints on the images [24, 25, 26, 27]. Although the accuracy of ROM calculation by digital photography is higher than that by traditional measurement methods, the convenience of this measurement is still a challenge. This is caused by the data transformation from the memory card to the computer. In addition, smartphone applications (Apps) have been proposed as an alternative to measure pathological shoulder ROM. These applications rely on internal smartphone inclinometers or photographic virtual goniometers to measure ROM [28, 29].

Fig. 4: Processing of angle calculation

Fig. 5: Definition of flexion and abduction.

B. Kinect-Based AROM Measurement

At present, Kinect, as a cheap sensing device for detecting human skeleton movement, has been widely used in computer games and rehabilitation training. Because Kinect does not need any physical contact with the subjects, and it is portable, accurate and easy to use. F. A. Matsen successfully applied Kinect to the measurement of active shoulder movement, and verified the feasibility of Kinect in the measurement of human AROM [30]. But this system requires the subjects to do certain postures, which is not fun for the subjects. In order to improve the fun of the game, we designed a wipe game using Kinect to stimulate the interest of the elderly.

III. OVERALL DESIGN OF OUR SYSTEM

The system consists of three parts: the game part, the sensor part and the AROM measurement part. When the older adults play the game, their joint motion will be recognized and the coordinates are collected by the sensor, then the coordinate will be introduced into ROM measurement part for calculation, thus achieving the automatic measurement of AROM.

A. Game Part

In the automatic AROM measurement system, scene transition, equipment layout and game picture are shown in Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. You can resize the window frame based on the width of the user's arm. Therefore, this system is suitable for any users. When the users want to reset the frame width, they just need to open their hands to make appropriate position, and then make OK gesture for confirmation. The setting method of window frame height is the same.

In the wiping area on the screen, the RGB image captured by Kinect is covered by transparent yellow texture. When the wiping game begins, Kinect will

recognize hands, the dirty position corresponding to the hands' coordinate will become clean. When the cleanliness achieves the pre-setting standard within the allotted time, the user will success to the next level. After the predetermined time, the game will end and the results will be published.

In the game pattern, to change the color of dirt on glass from transparent color to translucent yellow improve the visibility and the desire for the older adults to wipe a window. It is necessary to clean the furthest corner of the window to pass the game successfully. Because the movement distance of the hand is an arc, the participants must strive to improve the shoulder position to wipe the window corner, then the real upper limb' AROM value of the elderly can be obtained.

B. Sensor Part

About the convenience of our system, it needs only one staff to assist the elderly to link the equipment with computer and screen, operate the computer and double-click to open the game. The participants just need to sit on the chair and wipe the windows in front of the screen. The system will capture the coordinate of the human upper limb joints through Kinect, preserve the joint coordinate data of spine, shoulders, elbows in real time. With the coordinates, the AROM will be calculated as described in the next section, and the results will be saved automatically. The AROM value can be saved according to the time and the elderly's name, which is helpful for the medical staff to acquire the changes of the upper limbs' AROM in a period of time.

C. AROM Measurement Part

The measurement of AROM is performed according to the Japanese Association of Rehabilitation Medicine's measurement method about the flexion of the shoulder joint (raised in front of the body) and the abduction of the shoulder joint (raised from the side of the body) [31].

In this study, we define the angles of flexion and abduction between two lines, and the line 1 is from the right shoulder to the left shoulder; the line 2 is from shoulder to elbow (shown as Fig. 4). When the angle formed by the projected line of line 1 to the horizontal plane and the projected line of line 2 to the same plane becomes more than 45 degrees, the angle is defined as flexion. When the angle is less than 45 degrees, it is defined as abduction (shown as Fig. 5). The three-dimensional coordinate data of the human joint was used for angle calculation. As showed below, the angle

Fig. 6: Data Comparison Result between System Value and Goniometer Value. (A) Flexion data; (B) Abduction data. The experiment was performed with ten participants (8 normal and 2 hemiplegic subjects) and both shoulders were measured. The left shoulder's data of 2 hemiplegic participants were invalid and a few of metical data were same.

between vector A and vector B is shown as equation (1):

$$\theta = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{A \cdot B}{|A| \cdot |B|}\right) \quad (1)$$

III. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

A. Environment

The platform of the system is programmed with Unity 11, a “game development ecosystem” which can create interactive 3D and 2D content.

The hardware for this system in the experiment:

- A Microsoft© Kinect sensor V2, which includes a powered hub and USB cabling.
- A PC with Microsoft© Windows V8 or later with the Kinect drivers installed and the next recommended:
 - 8 GB Memory.
 - CPU: Intel® Core™ i7-4510U.
 - USB 3.0 controller dedicated to the Kinect for Windows V2 sensor.
 - GPU: NVIDIA GeForce® 840 M.

B. The Experiment of Automatic AROM Detection System and Results

The experiment was performed with ten older adults

(five males and five females, two hemiplegic persons among them). Their AROM were measured by our automatic AROM measurement system. Meanwhile, their PROM were measured with a goniometer by nurse. The average difference of flexion value between AROM and PROM is 21.6 degrees. And the average difference of abduction value between AROM and PROM is 24.1 degrees. The details of our system measurement values and goniometer measurement values are showed in Fig.6. The point on the line of $y=x$ means system values equal to goniometer values. The points locating at the area above the line means system values are larger than goniometer values. On the contrary, the point locating at the area below the line means system values are lower than goniometer values. It can be clearly concluded that no matter in the flexion measurement or abduction measurement, most of the points locate above the line. In the abduction measurement result shown in figure, one user’s abduction value is 0, which is caused by the poor recognition of Kinect on the clothing of the user.

A. Questionnaire Analyzing

In this paper, we develop an automatic AROM measurement system for the older adults based on a wiping game. And the result implies that the older adults stretched much better in the wiping game than in the measurement of goniometer. We proposed the fun

of measurement method can not only improve the authenticity of ROM, but also stimulate their participation in the measurement. To further improve the system, a questionnaire survey to the older adults was performed. As the results showed in table I, among the 17 elderly people who participated in the system from their interest. This may also explain why the ROM measurement value in our system is higher than goniometer measurement value.

To make the factors affecting their interest clear, we set 11 questions that may be relative to their interest, and each question has 5 levels. In order to know the main factors that affect their interest, we firstly did factor analysis, which was performed by SPSS software to extract 4 principle components from 11 questions. The factor loadings of the results are shown in table II. We named component 1 in table II as game's merit factor (F1). Four indexes are included in F1 as shown in table V, such as relieve stress, head gymnastics, rehabilitation and friend competition. We named component 2 in table II as game's design factor (F2). F2 including four indexes such as screen beauty, easy to understand, like gymnastics and with a score. We named component 3 in table II as elderly's physiology factor (F3). F3 including two indexes such as exercise intensity and pain. We named component 4 in table II as elderly's character factor (F4). F4 including one index that if they feel shy to do the game with other people. As shown in table II, the explaining variance accounted for 81% of all. Thus, the explanatory ability of the principle components from the questionnaire is outstanding.

TABLE I QUESTIONNAIRE RESULT OF INTERESTING VALUE

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	General	4	24
	Interesting	6	35
	Very Interesting	7	41
	Total	17	100

TABLE II TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED*

Component	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	Variance %	Cumulative %	Total	Variance %	Cumulative %
	1	4.50	41	41	2.85	26
2	1.94	18	59	2.75	25	51
3	1.34	12	71	1.87	17	68
4	1.14	10	81	1.45	13	81

*Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

TABLE III TOTAL MODEL SUMMARY

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.89	.79	.71	.43	2.36

TABLE IV COEFFICIENT

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	4.18	.11		
game's merit factor	.36	.11	.44	3.31	.00
game's design factor	.57	.11	.70	5.23	.00
elderly's physical factor	-.17	.11	-.21	-1.54	.15
elderly's character factor	.19	.11	.24	1.76	.10

TABLE V FACTOR COMPONENT

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Stress	.885	.325	.012	-.116
Head gym	.877	.099	-.125	.108
Rehabilitation	.719	.271	.196	-.403
Interesting competition	.691	.353	-.440	.172
Screen beauty	.226	.911	.006	.044
Simple picture	.250	.874	-.255	.189
Gymnastics	.122	.655	.303	-.544
Score	.365	.605	-.296	.057
Exercise intense	.079	-.077	.838	.065
Pain	-.184	-.069	.816	-.060
Shy	-.005	.192	.087	.945

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

Then we used multiple linear regression to determine the quantitative relationship between the interesting

level and the four principal components extracted from 11 questions. The regression coefficients between each independent variable and a dependent variable are shown in table III. $R=0.89$, it means a strong connection between satisfaction and each influenced factor. Determinant coefficient R Square equals to 0.79, it means that 79% of the information can be expressed well by the extracted factors in this model. According to the coefficients of each variable showed in table IV, the model can be written as equation (2).

$$y=4.176+0.358F_1+0.566F_2-0.167F_3+0.191F_4+\mu \quad (2)$$

In which y is the question of interesting about the system and μ is random error. From the equation (2), we can see the game function factor and game interesting factor greatly affect the experience of players in the game. These provide the original ideas for us to improve our system in future.

III. CONCLUSION

A new game-based upper limb AROM measurement system for older adults has been successfully developed using Kinect. The result showed the average flexion value of AROM is 21.6 degrees larger than the flexion value of PROM. And the average abduction value of AROM is 24.1 degrees larger than the abduction value of PROM. From the questionnaire, it seems that the interest of participant on the game is the reason to make themselves to be stretched much better than in the measurement using goniometer. Now to apply this system in rehabilitation is under studying.

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